

THEORETICAL STUDY OF BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF 1-(4-BROMOPHENOXY) PROPYNE-2

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Abstract. In the current developing period, in conjunction with the study of the chemical composition of each compound, it is also required to study its pharmacological activities. Because so far, many exchanged arylpropargyl ethers have been synthesized that manifest different biological activity in themselves, and their biological activity has not been fully studied. Naturally, in the current period, research on the pharmacological activity of a particular substance requires a huge amount of funds. Therefore, it is advisable to first determine the activity of substances using computer programs in the “structure-biological activity” method, and then study it “in vitro” or “in vivo” depending on the results. Therefore, in this study, the results of studying the biological activities of 1-(4-bromophenoxy)propyne-2 through the PASS (online) program are presented.

Keywords: pharmacological activity, pharmacological inactivity, Pass (Prediction of activity spectra for substances), biological activity, inhibitor, arylpropargyl esters.

Annotatsiya. Hozirgi rivojlanayotgan davrda har bir birikmaning kimyoviy tarkibini o‘rganish bilan birgalikda uning farmakologik faolliklarini ham o‘rganish talab qilinadi. Chunki hozirgi paytgacha har xil biologik faollikni o‘zida namoyon etadigan ko‘plab almashingan arilpropargil efirlari sintez qilingan va ularning biologik faolliklari esa to‘liq o‘rganilmagan. Tabiiyki hozirgi davrda ma‘lum bir moddaning farmakologik faolligini tadqiq qilish juda katta mablag‘ talab qiladi. Shuning uchun dastlab moddalarning “struktura-biologik faollik” usulida kompyuter dasturlari yordamida faolliklarini aniqlash, keyin esa natijalarga qarab “in vitro” yoki “in vivo” usulida o‘rganish maqsadga muvofiqdir. Shu sababli ushbu tadqiqotimizda PASS (onlayn) dasturi orqali 1-(4-bromfenoksi)propin-2 ning biologik faolliklarini o‘rganish natijalari keltirilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: farmakologik aktivlik, farmakologik inaktivlik, Pass (Prediction of activity spectra for substances), biologik faollik, ingibitor, arilpropargil efiri.

Аннотация. В настоящее время разработка требует изучения химического состава каждого соединения, а также его фармакологической активности. Потому что до сих пор было синтезировано много замещенных арилпропаргильных эфиров, которые проявляют различную биологическую активность, а их биологическая активность до конца не изучена. Естественно, что в нынешний период исследования фармакологической активности того или иного вещества требуют немалых средств. Поэтому целесообразно сначала определить активность веществ методом “структурно-биологической активности” с помощью компьютерных программ, а затем, в зависимости от результатов, изучить их методом “in vitro” или “in vivo”. Вот почему в этом исследовании представлены результаты изучения биологической активности 1-(4-бромфенокси)пропина-2 с помощью программы PASS (онлайн).

Ключевые слова: фармакологическая активность, фармакологическая неактивность, Pass (Прогнозирование спектров активности веществ), биологическая активность, ингибитор, арилпропаргильные эфиры.

INTRODUCTION

Predicting the biological activity of chemical compounds plays an important role in finding drugs and developing new bioactive molecules. For example, one such computational tool, the PASS (online) program, works on the principle of predicting their biological activity based on the structure of substances. These tools allow researchers to predict the biological activity of the compound with a high degree of reliability, reducing the need for a comprehensive range in the early stages of drug production, from laboratory research to tests performed in a living organism.

In this study, a theoretical analysis of the biological activity of 1-(4-bromophenoxy)propyne-2 is conducted using the PASS online program. This compound, an aryl propargyl ether, has a bromophenyl group attached to a propargyl unit through an oxygen atom. The presence of both the bromine atom and the propargyl unit suggests that this molecule may exhibit a range of biological activities, such as antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, or anticancer properties, due to its potential for interaction with biological targets through both electronic and structural features.

The PASS online program predicts the biological activity of a compound based on its structural formula, providing insight into possible pharmacological effects, mechanisms of action, and toxicological properties. Using this computational tool, this study aims to theoretically assess the biological activity of 1-(4-bromophenoxy)propyne-2, defining its potential as a bioactive molecule. This theoretical prediction serves as the basis for further experimental research and directs future research towards the practical application of the compound in the development of medicinal chemistry and medicines.

Through this theoretical study, a detailed understanding of the possible biological effects of 1-(4-bromophenoxy)propyne-2 can be obtained, which means that it can open up new pathways for its use in therapeutic fields.

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OBTAINED

The principle of operation of the PASS online program is based on structure-biological activity. In cases where the pharmacological activity is higher than the value $Pa > 0.7$, the substance's activity is more likely to be higher compared to the given diseases [1].

Scientific studies of the biological activity of halogen-exchanged arylpropargyl ethers and their effects on inhibitory and human health in chemical reactions have found that 1-(4-bromophenoxy)propyne-2 has several beneficial properties, but their mechanism of action has not yet been fully studied. In this work, the results of the study of some biological activity of 1-(4-bromophenoxy) propyne-2 using the PASS(online)program are presented. In these obtained results, it was mainly found that the substance has inhibitory property in various processes [2].

Table 1

Table of activity obtained in the Pass (online) program of 1-(4-bromophenoxy)propyne-2

№	Pa	Pi	Activity
1	0,913	0,006	Aspulvinone dimethylallyltransferase inhibitor
2	0,893	0,001	Stimulant of parathyroid hormone secretion
3	0,870	0,005	Feruloyl esterase inhibitor
4	0,836	0,006	Prolyl aminopeptidase inhibitor
5	0,753	0,005	Centromere-associated protein inhibitor
6	0,716	0,004	Skeletal muscle relaxant

7	0,711	0,041	Chymosin inhibitor
8	0,711	0,041	Acrocyllindropepsin inhibitor
9	0,711	0,041	Saccharopepsin inhibitor
10	0,705	0,039	Chlordecone reductase inhibitor

Diagram 1. Biological activity of 1-(4-bromphenoxy)propyne-2 as calculated in the PASS (online) program

Aspulvinone dimethylallyltransferase inhibitor. Aspulvinone is a dimethylallyltransferase inhibitor. In enzymology, aspulvinone dimethylallyltransferase (EC 2.5.1.35) is an enzyme that catalyzes a chemical reaction.

Thus, the two substrates of this enzyme are dimethylallyl diphosphate and aspulvinone E, and its two products are diphosphate and aspulvinone H [3].

Parathyroid hormone. Parathyroid hormone (PTH), also called parathormone or parathyrin, is a peptide hormone secreted by the parathyroid glands that regulates serum calcium concentration through its effects on bones, kidneys, and intestines [4].

Feruloyl esterase inhibitor. The enzyme feruloyl esterase (EC 3.1.1.73) catalyzes the reaction.

This enzyme belongs to the family of hydrolases, specifically enzymes that act on carboxylic ester bonds [5].

Prolyl aminopeptidase inhibitor. Prolyl aminopeptidase (EC 3.4.11.5, Proline aminopeptidase, Pro-X aminopeptidase, cytosol aminopeptidase V, Proline iminopeptidase) is an enzyme. This enzyme catalyzes the reaction of the release of N-terminal Proline from the peptide. This enzyme requires a Mn^{2+} ion to function [6].

According to this program, the activity of aspulvinone dimethylallyltransferase inhibitors within the studied activities of 1-(4-bromphenoxy)propyne-2 has higher activities compared to those where the Pa value remains above 0.9, as well as in the substrates of the remaining

inhibitors, as well as feruloyl esterase inhibitors and prolyl aminopeptidase inhibitors, Pa values above 0.8.

Table 2

Table of toxicity obtained in the Pass (online) program of 1-(4-bromphenoxy)propyne-2

№	Pa	Pi	Activity
1	0,828	0,012	Psychomotor disorder
2	0,683	0,018	Hypomagnesemia
3	0,657	0,025	Muscle weakness
4	0,636	0,051	Reproductive dysfunction
5	0,612	0,047	Weakness
6	0,587	0,025	Non-mutagenic, salmonella
7	0,583	0,047	Cyanosis
8	0,555	0,021	Spermicide
9	0,527	0,050	Hypothermic
10	0,512	0,060	Cataract

Diagram 1. Biological inactivity of 1-(4-bromphenoxy)propyne-2 as calculated in the PASS (online) program

According to the results obtained, this substance recorded the values of biological inactivation in relation to medical diseases such as psychomotor disorder, hypomagnesemia, muscle weakness, reproductive dysfunction and spermicide.

Psychomotor disorder. Psychomotor disorder is characterized by a slowdown in thinking in an individual and a decrease in physical activity. This can cause significant slowing of physical and emotional reactions, including speech and affect. Psychomotor retardation is often seen in people with severe depression and in the depressive phase of bipolar disorder. It is also associated with adverse effects of certain drugs such as benzodiazepines [7].

Hypomagnesemia. Hypomagnesemia is a medical condition characterized by abnormally low levels of magnesium in the blood. Magnesium is an important mineral that plays a crucial role in various functions in the body, including muscle and nerve function, energy production and bone normal development. Hypomagnesemia can be caused by factors such as an improper

diet, gastrointestinal disorders that affect magnesium absorption, or certain medications that reduce magnesium levels [8].

Muscle weakness. Muscle weakness is a lack of muscle strength. Its causes are many and can be divided into conditions that have either true or perceived muscle weakness. True muscle weakness is a primary symptom of a variety of skeletal muscle diseases, including muscular dystrophy and inflammatory myopathy. It occurs in neuromuscular junction disorders, such as myasthenia gravis. Muscle weakness can also be caused by low levels of potassium and other electrolytes within muscle cells. It can be temporary or long-lasting (from seconds or minutes to months or years). The term myasthenia is from my- from Greek μυο meaning "muscle" + -asthenia ἀσθένεια meaning "weakness" [9].

Spermicide. A spermicide is a contraceptive substance that destroys sperm that is inserted vaginally before intercourse to prevent pregnancy. A spermicide can be used alone as a contraceptive. However, couples who used only spermicide experienced a higher pregnancy rate than couples who used other methods. Usually, spermicides are combined with barrier methods of contraception such as diaphragms, condoms, cervical caps, and sponges. Combined methods have a lower pregnancy rate than either method alone. Spermicides are usually odorless, transparent, tasteless, non-staining and lubricating [10].

EXPERIENCE SECTION

To study the biological activity of halogen-exchanged arylpropargyl ethers, including 1-(4-bromophenoxy)propin-2, using the PASS (online) program, the following sequences are carried out to study the pharmacological activity against certain diseases: when working with the PASS (online) program, initially, this online platform undergoes registration. Then we enter the account that we have registered by pressing the "GO for prediction" Button and, by pressing the "Predict new compound" button, we draw our substance in "Marvin JS" and when we Press The predict button, we extract a table on the biological activity of our substance, after which a table of toxicity of the substance is also obtained.

CONCLUSION

When the biological activities of 1-(4-bromophenoxy) propin-2 were studied in the Pass(online)program compared to other inhibitors, the aspulvinone dimethylalyltransferase inhibitor was found to be significantly biologically active, exhibiting biological inactivations for psychomotor disorder, hypomagnesemia, muscle weakness, and reproductive dysfunction, i.e., similar medical diseases. It has been theoretically studied that the inclusion of different functional groups in the molecule of exchanged arylpropargyl ethers can cause an increase in its pharmacological activity, as well as a decrease in its inactivation [11].

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